

Paying Attention to the Fact That the Constructive Solution of the Cultural and Educational Centers Indicated In the Project Idea Depends On the Sketch Design

S. A. Qodirova¹, L. Sh. Raximov², N. H. Mirzaahmedova³, N. F. Fayzullayev⁴

¹Associate Professor, *Tashkent Institute of Architecture and Civil Engineering*

^{2,3}Assistant, *Tashkent Institute of Architecture and Civil Engineering*

⁴Student *Tashkent Institute of Architecture and Civil Engineering*

ABSTRACT: The buildings of the cultural and educational center are intended to promote large-scale cultural and educational programs among the general public. At the same time, it plays a dominant role as a main building in rural and urban population centers, as it unites and brings together all segments of the population.

KEYWORDS: cultural and educational center, evacuation, galleries, building, functional zones, sketch design.

INTRODUCTION

The main goal of the study is to develop design methods for the expression of the rich culture of Uzbekistan in modern buildings in the context of historic cities, including the identification of the main forms of architecture of Khorezm region. The scientific and practical study of the history of the formation of cultural and educational centers, as well as its social nature and architectural solutions is provided. The volumetric plan layout of the cultural and educational building, as well as its structure and opinions on the building's components, are discussed.

MAIN PART

One of the most pressing issues of our time is the rise in the number of meeting places, such as cultural and educational buildings, where people can spend their leisure time. Therefore, the cultural and educational building intended for the project is one of the architecturally perfect public buildings of cultural institutions in these areas, adapted for construction in villages and cities. According to the studied normative documents, cultural and educational centers are divided into the following types depending on their location and capacity:

Preservation of our national architectural heritage in the design process is an important element of the problem of complex urban planning activities of Uzbek architects. The use and operation of the building and its areas should not interfere with the historical and natural environment, but rather isolate the building inside the building, establish conditions for the demonstration of cultural, historical, and artistic values, provide a clear explanation of the building, and introduce it to both visitors and professionals.

Evacuation routes - horizontal and vertical (internal corridors, galleries, stairs), exits, including exits during the accident, must meet the requirements of SNQ 2.01.02 and these norms. Evacuation routes include elevators and escalators, as well as SNQ 2.01.02. Does not include the listed areas.

Evacuation routes will be illuminated in accordance with QMQ 2.01.05 and shall be equipped with directional devices that emit light for at least 1 hour when the main power supply is switched off.

The entrance to the building, as a rule, should be protected from atmospheric precipitation, the entrance area should be horizontal, non-slip, the water grate should be at the same level as the floor level of the small cage (cage size not exceeding 1.5 cm).

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On the external stairs (or sections of them) of the building wing, side handrail barriers with a height of 0.8-0.9 m should be mounted (the type of barriers is acceptable depending on the specific conditions). SNQ 2.07.02 needs wheelchair access, primarily ramps with handrail barriers, for wheelchair users.

If the width of the open stairs of the building wing exceeds 2.5 m, additional separating handrails must be installed.

The area in front of the main entrance door to the building and the main entrance drum should, as a rule, not be less than 2.2x1.8 m; the area of the evacuation exit from the building should not be less than 1.6x1.6 m (taking into account the requirements for access for the disabled according to SHNK 2.07.02).

The device of internal stairs (type 1) and open (type 2) placed in the stairwell must meet the requirements of SNQ 2.01.02 (including the slope of the stairs in the evacuation corridors, the width of the exit and the height of the steps, etc.). It is not possible to use steps of different heights and widths in the stair march.

It is appropriate to use curved main stairs, but the narrow part of the steps in the turn must have a minimum exit width of 22 cm.

Figure 1. Cultural and educational center building

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